

Moving Target Defense (MTD) for 6G Edge-to-Cloud Continuum: A Cognitive Perspective

Wissem Soussi, *Student Member, IEEE*, Gürkan Gür, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Burkhard Stiller, *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—The emergence of 6G networks will pave the way for a diverse range of services to function within virtualized multi-cloud environments in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum. This flexible and distributed architecture presents numerous prospects for enhancing service attributes such as availability, fault tolerance, and security. One primary instrument to this end is Moving Target Defense (MTD) as a security and resilience technique. However, MTD also poses an optimization challenge that extends beyond bolstering security alone and calls for smart and cognitive control. This paper elaborates on key technical topics regarding cognitive MTD in the 6G Edge-to-Cloud Continuum, including multi-objective modeling, RL-based control, and MTD peculiarities in 6G. We specifically highlight key technical challenges and identify potential directions for future research. As a concrete example, we present a Multi-objective Deep Reinforcement Learning (MORL) method to learn an optimal MTD strategy. Finally, we provide its preliminary performance evaluation in a 5G test bed embedding some key technologies applicable to future 6G networks, namely virtualized functions and AI-enhanced management and orchestration. The experimental results highlight the significance of MORL optimization over traditional deep-RL algorithms in this context.

Index Terms—Moving Target Defense (MTD), 6G security, ML for security, Edge-to-Cloud continuum, Security management.

I. INTRODUCTION

The next generation of wireless communications, envisaged as 6G or NextG networks, will integrate novel technologies and techniques such as Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), blockchain, native AI, Internet of Everything (IoE), quantum computing/communication and ubiquitous cloudification [1]. It will also provide higher flexibility and more granular control of digital infrastructure and services compared to previous generations. This is primarily due to the adoption of cloud technologies, such as virtualization and software-defined networking (SDN). Nevertheless, adopting cloud-native computing comes with considerable benefits as well as a greater risk of security vulnerabilities and impactful threats, emerging already as a pressing issue with 5G developments [2].

Additionally, networks are expanding to a more distributed infrastructure using resources from edge to cloud domains. This architectural setting is expected to be a fundamental attribute of 6G networks. It allows mobile applications to utilize cloud computing platforms located in intermediate data centers and edge networks near end-users, as well as in cloud data

centers. This Edge-to-Cloud continuum significantly reduces communication overload, and end-user Quality-of-Experience (QoE) is enhanced. However, the larger infrastructure that is eventually created also presents new challenges, as it increases the network’s attack surface. Consequently, managing and securing the services along the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum becomes increasingly critical.

The security of 6G/NextG networks can be strengthened by the Moving Target Defense (MTD) approach to tackle these problems. MTD is based on the principle of constantly changing the network’s configuration and assets to make it harder for attackers to exploit vulnerabilities. One key advantage of MTD is that it can disrupt the attackers’ ability to collect network intelligence and plan attacks. This increases the uncertainty for attackers and reduces their chances of success. However, enforcing MTD operations can also impact network performance and come with additional operational costs and energy consumption. Therefore, smart and dynamic control of MTD following a cognitive paradigm (i.e., a closed loop of *observing, orienting, planning, deciding, acting, and learning* tasks) considering security requirements, security gains, overhead, and feasibility is crucial.

This work provides an overview of MTD and its potential applications in modern networks for security and resilience. It elaborates on cognitive MTD relying on Deep Reinforcement Learning (deep-RL), which is promising for bolstering 6G security. This is attributed to the nature of the optimization problem at hand and the absence of ground truth for inference. Technical challenges and prospective research directions are discussed to integrate cognitive MTD solutions in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum of future networks. The novel framework “MERLINS” for optimizing MTD using deep-RL is introduced, to find a trade-off between improving security, reducing operational costs, and sustaining network performance.

II. TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

This section describes the MTD concept for network security, followed by a concise overview of the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum and the deep RL’s role in modeling and optimizing MTD strategies.

A. MTD in Network Security

The US National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) defines MTD as “the concept of controlling change across multiple system dimensions in order to increase uncertainty and apparent complexity for attackers, reduce their window of opportunity, and increase the costs of their probing and attack efforts.” MTD is implemented across various

Wissem Soussi is with the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW) and the University of Zurich (UZH), Switzerland. e-mail: wissem@zhaw.ch

Gürkan Gür is with the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), Institute of Computer Science (InIT), Switzerland. e-mail: gueu@zhaw.ch

Burkhard Stiller is with the Communication Systems Group CSG, Department of Informatics IH, University of Zurich UZH, Switzerland. e-mail: stiller@ifi.uzh.ch

Fig. 1: MTD operation types in a network.

domains, including software, *e.g.*, the Address Space Layout Randomization (ASLR) defending software’s code segments against memory-based attacks, and networking technologies encompassing wireless, wired, and hybrid networks. This technique can modify various elements present in a network, such as IP addresses, port numbers, proxies, virtual machines, containers, operating systems, software programs, protocols, and packet headers. MTD operations are classified into three categories: shuffling, diversity, and redundancy, as illustrated in Figure 1. The first category aims to disorient malicious users by changing the layout of the infrastructure. The second category aims to modify the attack surface of the infrastructure by changing the technology used for a running service. The final category aims to improve the fault tolerance and availability of the service by using multiple instances of a service.

Ultimately, MTD proactively eliminates the advantage that attackers can gain through passive and active reconnaissance attacks performed with scanning tools like *p0f*, *Nmap*, *Nessus*, and reactively mitigates detected attacks and anomalies. MTD works in conjunction with traditional security methods, such as firewalls, security protocols, authentication, and encryption, thereby enhancing resilience. In the context of 6G networks, multiple MTD methods cover three identified layers of an Edge-to-Cloud infrastructure, namely, the networking layer, the virtualization layer, and the application layer.

At the networking layer, MTD can change traffic routes using SDN control, substitute virtual switches for diversity (*e.g.*, swapping a Cisco virtual switch with an Open vSwitch with a different attack surface), and modify the network topology using NFV and proxy nodes. At the virtualization layer, MTD can relocate virtual resources to different cloud platforms, *e.g.*, moving a virtual network function (VNF) from an OpenStack Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) to a VMWare or an Azure VIM, thereby changing the topology and

virtualization stack upon which network functions execute.

B. Edge-to-Cloud Continuum and MEC

The combination of mobile, cloud, and edge computing technologies forms a computing continuum that enables new mobile services with stringent requirements such as augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR), Vehicle to Everything (V2X), and Tactile Internet (TI). These services are characterized by computational requirements that are not sustainable by the resources of the end user equipment (UE) or would significantly reduce the autonomy of battery-powered UEs, leading to the need to outsource the computational tasks to edge nodes within the latency requirements of critical services. Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) [3], specified by the European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI), establishes a standardized ecosystem connecting telecommunication providers, cloud vendors, and IT services. This is extended to the more general paradigm of Edge-to-Cloud Continuum, where a unified computing, communication, and storage fabric will optimally exploit the advantages of this distributed and flexible architecture in future networks.

Various security concerns are raised when dealing with the heterogeneity and the disposition of services in such a scenario. For instance, cellular base stations are generally installed in public places. Thus, they have fewer physical surveillance measures than traditional core networks, although the criticality of the edge node in the MEC disposition is high. Moreover, the cloud platform at the edge has reduced capabilities compared to typical data centers; thus, lightweight design and computational efficiency are desired security application requirements to maximize the functional usage of edge nodes.

C. Deep Reinforcement Learning

RL is a subset of Machine Learning (ML) that involves training an agent to optimize sequential decisions based on experience. The agent learns by interacting with its environment, observed and modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) – a tuple (S, A, P, R, γ) where S is the set of states of the environment, A is the set of actions that the agent can take, P is the transition probability matrix defining the probability that an action a_i changes a state s_i to a new specific state s_j , R is a set of reward values for all (a_i, s_i) pairs and γ is the discount factor defining the importance of the immediate rewards over the future rewards. The agent’s goal is to learn an optimal policy that maximizes the cumulative reward. RL has seen evolutionary advances through the usage of deep neural networks (DNN) leading to deep-RL algorithms [4].

Conventional deep-RL algorithms, however, are designed for single-objective optimization and used with the scalarization of the different rewards corresponding to the different objectives into one reward value. This scalarization can be part of the missing information we want to learn, *i.e.*, the best trade-off among objectives to maximize the overall return. If the optimization occurs for only one fixed weighted sum, the result produced would be suboptimal as other weight sums are not explored. The scalarization can also depend on a user’s preference, which makes the weights a variable that should be

Fig. 2: Pareto front for three objectives showing the benefits of MO methods over weighted sum optimization methods (Adapted from [5]).

controlled. With legacy deep-RL, this is not possible unless a different model is trained with new weights. Moreover, the single scalarized value can be semantically meaningless as the multiple objectives are fundamentally different in nature. For instance, one objective can be to reduce an economic cost metric, measured in a monetary unit, while another objective is to improve proactive security, which may be measured in terms of the attack success probability (ASP) reduction of a threat. Merging both measures to a value that is hard to interpret leads to decisions that are also hard to interpret/explain.

Multi-Objective RL (MORL) is a new category of RL algorithms that keeps different interpretable reward functions, one for each objective, and iterates the optimization process on different weighted sums, avoiding suboptimal solutions and approximating the set of optimal policies for all scalarizations (see Figure 2). This solution set is defined as the *coverage set* (CS), which for monotonically increasing reward functions is reduced to the *Pareto Front* (PF) [6]. PF is the set of undominated solutions, where each solution is optimal with respect to a specific scalarization. MORL’s interactions to retrieve the PF occurs with a Multi-Objective MDP (MOMDP), where the main difference with respect to the MDP’s definition is that R is now a vector \bar{R} comprising the reward values of the multiple objectives defined in the model. These objectives do not always align with one another, since optimizing one objective may be done at the expense of others. In the scenario of MTD operations in the Edge-to-Cloud continuum, moving a resource to a closer node may improve latency, but it may also weaken security since its position becomes predictable to attackers. Conversely, a completely random move aimed at enhancing security could negatively affect the network and service performance. Therefore, in contrast to legacy deep-RL models, MORL allows learning the optimal trade-offs and enables the user to set his own preferences in terms of objective prioritization.

III. DEEP-RL OPTIMIZED MTD: RECENT WORK

Optimization of MTD operations in network security scenarios is already attracting a lot of attention from research and industrial communities. In the past, game theory-based MTD optimization strategies have been developed to counter various attack models in various environments, ranging from Partially Observable Markov Decision Processes (POMDP) in large-scale networks [7] to general-sum Markov Games in cloud networks [8]. Research on AI/ML-optimized MTD is relatively recent, aligned with game-theoretical methodologies that have a more established historical foundation and are still a necessary component to tackle the optimization problem with deep-RL. DQ-MOTAG [9] employs MTD IP shuffling to mitigate ongoing Distributed DoS (DDoS) attacks on web servers. It finds the original hidden malicious user giving up the server’s IP to other active attacking hosts with a minimal number of shuffles using deep-RL. DESOLATER [10] presents a multi-agent deep-RL method to train an MTD shuffling strategy of the IP address layout in in-vehicle networks with SDN capabilities. Microsoft has also contributed to advancing this research direction for local and enterprise networks by releasing the open-source research toolkit “Cyber-BattleSim” [11]. Aligned with the trajectory of this research, the new work presented in Section V introduces a MOMDP framework termed MERLINS [12]. MERLINS offers proactive and reactive protection of NFV resources by modeling the state of an Edge-to-Cloud environment in a MOMDP and enables the continual optimization and adaptation of sequential MTD actions through MORL. Table I summarizes the important aspects of related work.

IV. TECHNICAL CHALLENGES AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There exists a variety of pertinent research questions and challenges that must be confronted to facilitate and enhance the cognitive MTD approach within envisaged Beyond 5G (B5G)/6G networks. The focus is laid on the role of AI/ML, deep-RL in particular, in this domain. A concise depiction of these questions and challenges is provided in Figure 3, followed by more detailed discussions in the next subsections.

A. Dynamic Ultra-large-scale Networks

An inherent problem is essentially the complexity since 6G networks will be ubiquitous ultra-large-scale systems incorporating different systems, technologies, and devices, ranging from IoE to space networks [1]. Future networks operated by communication service providers (CSPs) will also exhibit a heterogeneous spectrum of hardware/software performance capabilities and requirements in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum. For instance, 6G-enabled remote surgery demands ultra-low latency (< 1 ms) and high edge computational power (from 100 Giga Operations Per Second (GOPS) to 1 TOPS) for real-time robot control, image processing, and haptic feedback utilizing Extended Reality (XR) interfaces. This translates to a need for high bandwidth (from 100 Mbps to 1 Gbps) for seamless graphical and sensory data transfer. In contrast, smart agriculture applications may leverage 6G MIMO technology operating in the 1-10 GHz frequency range to achieve higher

TABLE I: Recent Work and its Scope on MTD Optimization.

	Environment	Approach	Deep-RL	B5G/6G perspective	Edge-to-Cloud Security	Game theory	Multi-objective
Online Defense Algo [7]	Theoretical model	POMDP				✓	
Markov Game Model [8]	Cloud testbed	General-sum Markov Games			✓	✓	
DQ-MOTAG [9]	Cloud-hosted web app.	DQN	✓			✓	
DESOLATER [10]	In-vehicle network with SDN	Multi-agent deep-RL	✓		✓	✓	✓
CyberBattleSim [11]	Network simulation	MDP & deep-RL	✓			✓	
MERLINS [12]	5G testbed	MORL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

spatial resolution for Radio Access Points (RAN). However, it does not necessitate the stringent latency or bandwidth requirements of remote surgery and exhibits lower sensitivity to network instability. This inherent heterogeneity in service demands significantly influences the cost models associated with MTD actions, ultimately complicating the optimal MTD policy. Notably, negative effects of applying a uniform network performance approach could be significantly more detrimental to a service like remote surgery compared to smart agriculture.

Moreover, as there is the constraint to initially train the deep-RL model on a representative yet limited test bed, the model's performance must be subject to re-evaluation within the context of the network setting and requirements.

B. Data Challenges

The significance of data engineering during the MTD optimization process cannot be overstated. Given the diverse range of objectives under consideration for the optimization of the MTD strategy, a comprehensive aggregation of real-time data sourced from the network's monitoring infrastructure is necessary. Next, to harness the value of such data, it becomes imperative to establish a well-designed reward system. This system translates the collected data into quantifiable metrics that reflect the network's status toward the objectives outlined within the MOMDP (or any other objective modeling).

Furthermore, it is crucial to exercise caution, when training ML models on monitoring data of public networks. This practice carries the inherent risk of revealing sensitive information, such as end-user personal data, and impairing privacy. Consequently, vigilant safeguards must be implemented to avert any inadvertent data leakage from the model. Additionally, privacy-preserving data analytics techniques could be employed.

C. MTD in a Multi-tenant 6G Network

An envisioned advanced MTD design for 6G networks involves the integration of a multi-tenant federated MTD approach aimed at capitalizing on the diverse range of network experiences and threat intelligence of various CSPs. Different architectural patterns exist for such a federated solution. One approach entails a centralized MTD model operating within a hierarchical relationship among tenants/operators. An alternative perspective relies on a distributed MTD model characterized by a peer-to-peer (P2P) tenant structure, where independent decision-making systems function autonomously. While the former exhibits simplicity in implementation, it

requires trust and data transparency – frequently impossible to facilitate. In contrast, the latter P2P configuration offers tenants greater independence but amplifies the difficulties associated with intelligence sharing and interplay between disparate models. Another prospect is hybrid systems containing both federated and locally oriented decision-making systems. However, such approaches necessitate incorporating a conflict resolution system. For instance, a hierarchy could be established among these decision-making systems, prioritizing the local model over the federated one or vice versa.

D. Green Security

The exploration of energy-efficient MTD orchestration as another optimization objective constitutes a relevant research direction in light of environmental considerations pertaining to sustainable energy consumption and the overarching goal of achieving a global net-zero footprint and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). In this context, the integration of MTD techniques can consider the carbon emissions associated with network slices' activities, *e.g.*, by strategically placing VNFs within cloud nodes powered by green energy sources rather than fossil-fuel-powered nodes. Furthermore, the energy cost for MTD actions can be integrated into the optimization model.

E. Security/Transparency of Deep-RL Learned MTD Policies

While an MTD framework provides an additional layer of security to future networks, it can also be a new point of attack that can be exploited. The ML model, for instance, is a sensitive attack surface, as it can be sensible to hijacking, poisoning attacks during training, evasion techniques such as adversarial example attacks, or triggering meaningless MTD operations as a DoS attack and resource waste [1]. Measures can be implemented to safeguard data integrity and authenticate the origin of data, particularly from network endpoints providing monitoring data. Furthermore, the introduction of noise to ML predictions stands out as a potential strategy against model inversion attacks to MTD [1].

For technical, economic, and legal reasons, the decisions of the RL agents should also be humanly explainable (*i.e.*, with statistics and logic). For instance, the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) [13] emphasizes the explainability of AI and ML algorithms, especially DNNs, which are not explainable by nature. Integration of explainable AI into MTD remains an open research question. It is potentially possible to implement different explainable RL (XRL) methods present in

Fig. 3: Research Challenges and Directions for MTD in 6G.

the literature, such as the XRL via reward decomposition [14]. With this method, rewards can be classified according to semantically meaningful reward types, which fits well with the multi-objective nature of the MTD optimization problem.

V. MTD STRATEGY OPTIMIZATION WITH MORL: A PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

MERLINS [12] is a framework designed and implemented to perform MTD in an Edge-to-Cloud environment using two specific action types, namely, live migrations and re-instantiations of VNFs. It implements a cognitive closed loop for MTD control by monitoring, deciding on actions, enforcing them, and learning in a dynamic manner. As depicted in Figure 4, for each of the MOMDP objectives, the following methods and data are used:

1) *Proactive security:* A threat and risk assessment module is implemented. Such assessments of the running VNFs are made using vulnerability scanners to find and enumerate vulnerabilities using the Common Vulnerability Enumerations (CVEs) and Network Vulnerability Tests (NVTs) databases. For each VNF, the risks are quantified by grouping the vulnerabilities into major threats: *e.g.*, advanced persistent threats (APT), data leak, and DoS. For each threat, an ASP value is estimated and incremented with time, representing the attackers' advantage when the target is static. These are reset to their original values after an MTD action is performed on the VNF. Finally, the ASP value can be multiplied by a criticality factor given to each VNF by the network administrator to prioritize the security of some VNFs.

2) *MTD operational cost:* The cost of MTD actions such as migration and re-instantiation are measured by the additional resources used, such as CPU, RAM, and storage. The cost of such additional usage is estimated with an empirical study covering 66% of the worldwide cloud market in 2022 on VM prices in $\$/hour$ [12].

3) *Network performance and QoS:* To measure the QoS of moving services, MERLINS uses network probes to regularly collect network metrics and measure the variance in

Fig. 4: MORL-based MTD in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum.

the latency, connection throughput, and packet loss rate of communications between VNFs and client UEs.

Based on the measurements performed on a multi-cloud 5G test bed, the operational cost of a single MTD action (*i.e.*, re-instantiation and live migration) in MERLINS are sustainable even in stringent scenarios such as those of remote surgery mentioned in Section IV-A, providing some conditions are met, such as 1) communication via HTTP/3 and not HTTP/2 and 2) The edge VNF used by the application is stateless (*i.e.*, can restart from the base image) [15].

A. Experimental Test Bed

The experimentation occurs within a multi-cloud 5G network. While this is not a 6G test bed per se, we focus on a configuration that will be relevant for future networks, such as the TelcoCloud setup using NFV and cloud-native infrastructure, the virtualization of the 5G core network functions, the network slicing, and the distribution of services across the edge following the MEC standard. The test bed configuration contains a pair of network slices: one confined to the private domain and the other to the shared operator's domain [12]. While the private network slice contains the VNFs related to the 5G core, the public network slice accommodates the

operation of four VNFs, increasing and decreasing in numbers during the experiment. MERLINS’s monitoring and MTD operations are performed on the latter slice, as the current focus is MTD operations on stateless services and the private network slice contains stateful services such as the User Plane Function (UPF).

This network environment is hosted within a MEC architecture that spans the continuum from edge to cloud with two distinct OpenStack NFVIs: the Core NFVI hosts the 5G core Open5GS system, while the Edge NFVI accommodates the distributed UPF, alongside edge VNFs of the private network slice. The Radio Access Network (RAN) and end-user devices are simulated through UERANSIM. The orchestration of NFV resources is executed by leveraging the ETSI Open Source MANO (OSM), while the network slice management is facilitated by [12].

B. Selected Performance Results

For proactive MTD protection, a comparative study is done by training four well-known single-objective deep-RL algorithms: advantage actor-critic (A2C), deep Q-learning (DQN), proximal policy optimization (PPO), and a PPO variation using a mask for dynamic action spaces (maskPPO); and two MORL algorithms: Envelope MORL and the expected utility policy gradient (EUPG) [12].

The performance of the models is compared with a Stackelberg Markov Game solver from the MTD framework by [8], finding the Strong Stackelberg Equilibrium (SSE), a random MTD policy (*baseline1*) and a knowledge-based MTD policy (*baseline2*). These agents are using the scalarized value of the three objectives, as in legacy deep-RL algorithms. The SSE solver has to calculate the full Q-value matrix and the reward values for all (state, action) pairs, imposing more rigorous constraints on the size limits of the MDP in contrast to its utilization with a deep-RL agent. To mitigate this problem in our experimental setup, we simplified the MDP model for the SSE solver and discretized continuous metrics to values such as ‘low’, ‘average’, or ‘high’ to avoid a state-space explosion due to high-range values. *Baseline2* follows an MTD strategy for the running VNFs based on the security priority level attributed to each VNF. It decides on the MTD action (*i.e.*, migration or re-instantiation) based on the availability constraint of a service.

The results in Figure 5 show clearly a better reward optimization when using the MORL algorithms compared to single-objective models. Only the Envelope MORL and EUPG algorithms learned a slightly better policy than *baseline2*. SSE and A2C appear to get stuck in a local minimum, avoiding performing any MTD action to circumvent the penalties of selecting an invalid action. The DQN policy learned that selecting the same MTD action is better as it resets the ASP values of the given VNF’s threats. However, since other VNFs are left with their threats increasing the ASP with time, the cumulative reward drops exponentially as shown in Figure 5. Both PPO and maskable PPO models learned to re-instantiate the VNFs defined as *most critical*, leading to an average reward per step of -0.39, greatly improving

(a) Continuous Management Performance of Deep-RL Models

RL model	\bar{x} rew/step	RL model	\bar{x} rew/step
SSE	-29	Baseline1	-0.44298
Baseline2	-0.2123	DQN	-0.647
A2C	-29	PPO-MLP	-0.39
MaskPPO-MLP	-0.39	EnvelopeMORL	-0.2114
EUPG	-0.1932		

(b) Average (\bar{x}) Reward per Step

Fig. 5: Cumulative Reward and Reward/Step.

over *baseline1* and improving the cumulative reward to a linear curb. *Baseline2* still performs better as it considers the availability constraint and follows a more distributed selection of VNFs, reaching this constraint less frequently. Envelope MORL’s policy demonstrates similar performance, moving critical VNFs more often and also moving all other VNFs evenly and with lower frequency. Finally, we identify the improvement of the EUPG model over Envelope MORL by its tendency to select re-instantiations over migrations, as the former has less network overhead than the latter.

C. Limitations and Discussion

The analysis of MERLINS runs through the lens of research challenges (*cf.* Section IV), highlights existing limitations of the proposed method, and suggests potential solutions for future research.

1) *Scalability*: In MORL, scalability is a relevant challenge, since the addition of multiple objectives increases the dimension of the MDP space to be explored during training. Another limitation of MORL is that MOMDP models are defined with a static number of states, and as networks dynamically change in size and shape, MOMDPs are not inherently adapted for network modeling. We address this issue in MERLINS by defining a number of MDP states equivalent to the maximal dimensions of the network infrastructure. This consequently leads to the action space of the MOMDP being dynamic: resources in the MDP that are yet non-existent in the actual network are considered idle and inaccessible states and actions for the deep-RL agent. This solution shifts the problem to the action space, which becomes dynamic as well, while it should

be static in MDPs. The action space shift is realized in MERLINS with the maskable actions of the maskPPO algorithm. However, this did not yield a significant improvement over the conventional PPO algorithm, while fixing the MOMDP to an oversized network might have affected the learning curve for smaller networks. While the used 5G test bed can approximate the scale of a private industrial 5G/6G network, public operators handling a huge number of VNFs face a more complex challenge. This complexity exacerbates the MORL learning process in the context of real-world public 6G networks. A prospective remedy to this limitation involves the learning of a solution set consisting of multiple models learned on different network sizes, rather than training a generalized *one-for-all* sizes policy.

2) *Data Challenges*: A very challenging problem is quantifying the abstract objectives with measurable data collected from the network. If the selected metrics, their relations, and aggregation to one value are not objectively correct, the learned model will be biased as the agent perceives the network's state incorrectly. While MERLINS collects data in direct relation to its MOMDP objectives, the aggregation of such data to one value per objective is not necessarily optimal. For instance, how to aggregate the latency shift, measured in milliseconds, with the packet loss rate shift, measured in percentage? Which operator is more suitable for aggregation: addition or multiplication? These choices need to be justified and are potential research topics.

3) *MTD in a Multi-tenant 6G Cloud*: MERLINS is tested on a single-tenant 5G cloud and still needs to consider the multi-tenant scenario. Various decentralization methods should be considered for federated ML and the decision-making process, as discussed in Section IV-C.

4) *Green Security*: MERLINS model does not consider the energy overhead at the moment, but it can be promptly integrated into the model once energy consumption profiles of different network elements in different slices are determined.

5) *AI security and Transparency*: Currently, MERLINS lacks defenses against adversarial attacks during the training and inference phases of its machine learning model. Additionally, MERLINS does not address the inherent challenge of explainability associated with NN-based models. As discussed in Section IV-E, methods such as authenticating the provenance of training data, employing ML robustness techniques like noisy model prediction, and utilizing explainability approaches, such as XRL for MORL explainability, can be leveraged to enhance the resilience and interpretability of the MERLINS framework.

VI. SUMMARY

Forthcoming 6G networks are anticipated to embody exceptional dynamism and heterogeneity, characterized by diverse device types, access technologies, and service provisions with cloud-native technologies. In such a multifaceted and evolving context, the upholding of seamless security is a formidable challenge. Thus, this paper presented MTD as a vital defense technique in this context and discussed a suitable AI-driven optimization as well as the automation of MTD strategies across the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported partially by (a) the University of Zürich UZH, Switzerland and (b) the Horizon Europe Framework Program's project NETWORK, Grant Agreement No. 101139285 funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation SERI, under Contract No. 22.00642.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Porambage, G. Gür, D. P. M. Osorio, M. Liyanage, A. Gurtov, and M. Ylianttila, "The roadmap to 6G security and privacy," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 2, pp. 1094–1122, 2021.
- [2] W. Soussi, M. Christopoulou, G. Xilouris, and G. Gür, "Moving target defense as a proactive defense element for beyond 5G," *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 72–79, 2021.
- [3] F. Jiang, K. Wang, L. Dong, C. Pan, W. Xu, and K. Yang, "AI driven heterogeneous MEC system with UAV assistance for dynamic environment: Challenges and solutions," *IEEE Network*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 400–408, 2021.
- [4] V. Mnih, K. Kavukcuoglu, D. Silver, A. A. Rusu, J. Veness, M. G. Bellemare, A. Graves, M. Riedmiller, A. K. Fidjeland, G. Ostrovski *et al.*, "Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning," *Nature*, vol. 518, no. 7540, pp. 529–533, 2015.
- [5] S. Smith, M. Southerby, S. Setiniyaz, R. Apsimon, and G. Burt, "Multiobjective optimization and pareto front visualization techniques applied to normal conducting RF accelerating structures," *Physical Review Accelerators and Beams*, vol. 25, no. 6, p. 062002, 2022.
- [6] C. F. Hayes, R. Rădulescu, E. Bargiacchi, J. Källström, M. Macfarlane, M. Reymond, T. Verstraeten, L. M. Zintgraf, R. Dazeley, F. Heintz *et al.*, "A practical guide to multi-objective reinforcement learning and planning," *Autonomous Agents and Multi-Agent Systems*, vol. 36, no. 1, p. 26, 2022.
- [7] E. Miebling, M. Rasouli, and D. Teneketzis, "A POMDP approach to the dynamic defense of large-scale cyber networks," *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 2490–2505, oct 2018.
- [8] S. Sengupta, A. Chowdhary, D. Huang, and S. Kambhampati, "General sum Markov games for strategic detection of advanced persistent threats using moving target defense in cloud networks," in *Decision and Game Theory for Security*, T. Alpcan, Y. Vorobeychik, J. S. Baras, and G. Dán, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 492–512.
- [9] X. Chai, Y. Wang, C. Yan, Y. Zhao, W. Chen, and X. Wang, "DQ-MOTAG: Deep reinforcement learning-based moving target defense against DDoS attacks," in *2020 IEEE Fifth International Conference on Data Science in Cyberspace (DSC)*. IEEE, Aug 2020, pp. 375–379.
- [10] S. Yoon, J.-H. Cho, D. S. Kim, T. J. Moore, F. Free-Nelson, and H. Lim, "DESOLATER: Deep reinforcement learning-based resource allocation and moving target defense deployment framework," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 70 700–70 714, 2021.
- [11] Microsoft Defender Research Team, "Cyberbattlesim," <https://github.com/microsoft/cyberbattlesim>, Tech. Rep., created by Christian Seifert, Michael Betsler, William Blum, James Bono, Kate Farris, Emily Goren, Justin Grana, Kristian Holsheimer, Brandon Marken, Joshua Neil, Nicole Nichols, Jugal Parikh. Accessed: 2024-10-15.
- [12] W. Soussi, M. Christopoulou, G. Gür, and B. Stiller, "MERLINS – moving target defense enhanced with deep-rl for nfV in-depth security," in *2023 IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (NFV-SDN)*, 2023, pp. 65–71.
- [13] European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), "Artificial intelligence and cybersecurity research," Tech. Rep., 2023, accessed: 2023-07-14. [Online]. Available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/artificial-intelligence-and-cybersecurity-research>

- [14] Z. Juozapaitis, A. Koul, A. Fern, M. Erwig, and F. Doshi-Velez, “Explainable reinforcement learning via reward decomposition,” in *IJCAI/ECAI Workshop on Explainable Artificial Intelligence*, 2019.
- [15] W. Soussi, M. Christopoulou, T. Anagnostopoulos, G. Gür, and B. Stiller, “Topofuzzer — a network topology fuzzer for moving target defense in the telco cloud,” in *NOMS 2023-2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium*, 2023, pp. 1–5.

Wissem Soussi is a research assistant at Zurich University of Applied Sciences ZHAW and a PhD student at the University of Zurich UZH, Switzerland. He received his B.S degree in Computer Sciences in 2018 from Montpellier University, and MSc. degree in Cybersecurity in 2020 from Grenoble University, France. His research interests are networks & systems security and ML/AI applied to cybersecurity.

Gürkan Gür is a senior lecturer at Zurich University of Applied Sciences ZHAW, Switzerland. He received his B.S. degree in electrical engineering in 2001 and Ph.D. degree in computer engineering in 2013 from Bogazici University, Turkey. His research interests include Future Internet, information security, next-generation wireless networks and cyberdefense.

Burkhard Stiller chairs the Communication Systems Group CSG, Department of Informatics IfI, University of Zürich UZH, as a Full Professor. He received his Diplom-Informatiker and Dr. rer.-nat. degrees, respectively, from the University of Karlsruhe, Germany. His main research interests include fully decentralized systems, including Blockchains, network and service management, IoT, and telecommunication economics.